

Auditable Private LLM Serving on Kubernetes: A Vendor-Neutral Architecture and Evidence Model for Regulated Environments

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Abstract—Regulated organisations increasingly want to run large language models on infrastructure they control. Self-hosting a model, however, is not the same as being able to prove how it was served. An auditor working under the EU AI Act, the Digital Operational Resilience Act (DORA), or the GDPR asks narrower questions than “is the model private”: which identity called which model, over what data, with what provenance, and where is the record that says so. We present a vendor-neutral reference architecture for private LLM serving on Kubernetes, together with an evidence model that turns these regulatory expectations into controls a machine can check. The architecture composes an inference gateway, GitOps delivery, and policy-as-code so that three controls, namely request lineage, access and model governance, and model provenance, each emit evidence a machine can check, including a redacted, queryable, tamper-evident audit trail. The evidence model regenerates a complete evidence pack with a single command and fails closed when the proof is missing or stale. We evaluate the design in three ways: a threat-to-control-to-evidence analysis, conformance checks that confirm forbidden actions are blocked and that a single altered audit record is detected, and a measurement of the runtime cost of the governance layer. On commodity CPU hardware the full governance path adds about 28 microseconds of processing per request, a sub-percent fraction of end-to-end latency once inference is in the path. In this setting the cost of making compliance provable is small and bounded.

Index Terms—private LLM serving, Kubernetes, compliance automation, audit, model provenance, policy-as-code, EU AI Act, DORA, GDPR, ISO/IEC 42001

I. INTRODUCTION

A bank that wants to use a language model for internal document search cannot simply send its documents to a hosted API. Neither can a hospital, a public administration, or a defence contractor. The reasons are familiar: data residency, confidentiality of the prompts themselves, and a growing list of legal obligations that attach to any organisation deploying an AI system in the European Union. The EU AI Act [1] requires record-keeping and traceability for higher-risk systems. DORA [2] requires financial entities to manage and evidence the operational resilience and supply chain of their information and communication technology. The GDPR [3] requires data minimisation and a record of processing activities. None of these is satisfied by the act of running a model in-house.

The common response is to self-host: deploy an open-weight model behind an inference server such as vLLM [4] on a cluster

the organisation controls. This solves data residency. It does not, by itself, produce any of the evidence an auditor will ask for. A self-hosted model with no access control, no request lineage, and no record of which artifact is actually running is private but not auditable. The gap we address is precisely this one: the distance between *private* and *provable*.

We argue that the questions a regulator or an internal auditor actually asks are narrow and technical, and that they can be answered automatically. They reduce to a triangle: *which identity* invoked *which model* over *which data*, and where is the tamper-evident record. If a platform can make each side of that triangle machine-checkable, then compliance stops being a binder of screenshots assembled before an audit and becomes a property the system emits continuously.

We build on an existing artifact, the PRIVATE-AI-PLATFORM-KIT, an open-source Kubernetes platform for private LLM serving, RAG, and coding-agent workspaces. The platform runs first on a local `kind` cluster with Ollama [5] and then, through the same Helm charts and GitOps layout, on customer-owned clusters with vLLM on GPU nodes. Using a runnable system rather than a paper design lets us measure the cost of the controls we propose and lets a reviewer reproduce that cost.

Our contribution is not a new serving engine and not a new policy language. It is the design that connects regulatory requirements to verifiable controls on a vendor-neutral substrate, and the measured demonstration that doing so is cheap. Concretely:

- We derive a compact set of twelve testable requirements (**R1** through **R12**) from the EU AI Act, DORA, the GDPR, and the NIST AI Risk Management Framework [6], cross-checked against the ISO/IEC 42001 management standard [7], each stated as a technical property rather than legal prose (Section III).
- We present a vendor-neutral architecture that realises these requirements through three controls, request lineage, access and model governance, and model provenance, with each design decision tied to a requirement and the rejected alternatives stated (Section IV).
- We define an *evidence model*: the mechanism by which requirements become evidence a machine can check. It

comprises redacted hash-chained audit records with an auditor query, an evidence pack regenerated by one command, reproducible provenance digests, policy-as-code admission, and release gates that fail closed on missing or stale proof (Section V).

- We evaluate the design along three axes: a threat-to-control-to-evidence analysis; conformance checks that show forbidden actions are blocked and that mutating one audit record is detected; and a measurement of the governance layer’s runtime cost, which is about 28 microseconds of CPU per request and a small fraction of end-to-end latency (Section VI).

We do not claim to make a model safe, correct, or unbiased. We make the narrower claim that the act of serving it can be governed and proven at negligible cost, and we show the numbers.

II. BACKGROUND AND THREAT MODEL

A. Regulatory drivers, stated technically

We treat three regulations, the EU AI Act, DORA, and the GDPR, together with two voluntary standards, the NIST AI Risk Management Framework and ISO/IEC 42001, as sources of requirements, and we read them for the technical obligations they impose rather than for legal interpretation.

The **EU AI Act** [1] requires, for higher-risk AI systems, automatic recording of events over the system’s lifetime (Article 12, logging and traceability, with logs retained for at least six months), technical documentation sufficient to assess conformity (Article 11 and Annex IV), and human oversight. Its obligations apply in phases: the duties on general-purpose model providers have applied since August 2025, and the higher-risk record-keeping and documentation duties phase in after that. For a serving platform the operative parts are the automatic record-keeping that survives scrutiny and the documentation of what is actually deployed. **DORA** [2], in force since January 2025, requires financial entities to manage information and communication technology risk, including access control, change management, and third-party and supply-chain risk, and to be able to evidence all of it. **The GDPR** [3] requires data minimisation (Article 5), security of processing (Article 32), and a record of processing activities (Article 30). **The NIST AI RMF** [6], with its Generative AI Profile [8], is not law but gives a vocabulary, in particular the *Map, Measure, Manage* functions, that lines up well with continuous evidence. **ISO/IEC 42001** [7] specifies an AI management system; it sits above the technical controls, and the machine-checkable evidence we generate is the operational record that such a management system, and an AI Act conformity assessment, consume.

A recurring pattern across all five is that the obligation is not only to behave correctly but to *demonstrate* that one did. This is the property we design for.

B. System model

The platform serves OpenAI-compatible chat-completion traffic. Requests enter an inference gateway, which authenticates

the caller, applies admission and model-routing policy, records metrics and a redacted audit event, and forwards the request to a runtime backend (Ollama for local CPU use, vLLM [4] for GPU clusters). Alongside the serving path the platform hosts retrieval-augmented generation and isolated coding-agent workspaces, each in its own Kubernetes namespace. Delivery onto Kubernetes [9] is by GitOps: an Argo CD [10] application syncs versioned Helm charts, and admission policy is enforced by Kyverno [11]. The same repository runs on a local `kind` cluster and on a customer-owned cluster; only the platform services the customer already operates (ingress, storage, secrets, observability, GPU pools) are substituted.

C. Trust boundaries and assumptions

We trust the Kubernetes control plane, the customer’s secret manager, and the cluster operators. We do not trust: external callers, the contents of the RAG corpus or any retrieved document, the network destinations a workload might try to reach, or the integrity of an artifact that arrives without provenance. We assume the customer wires the gateway’s authentication to their identity provider and replaces reference model digests with their own model-store digests before production; these are documented handoff steps rather than guarantees the platform makes on its own. We assume an honest-but-curious insider for the audit-tampering threat: someone with log access who might alter a record, not an attacker who has fully compromised the control plane.

D. Threats

Table I lists the threats we defend against and names the requirement that answers each. Three of them are specific to an AI platform and deserve a note. Indirect prompt injection (**T8**) arrives as data: instructions hidden in a retrieved document or a workspace file that the model then follows [12], [13]. Request-level authentication does nothing against it, because the request itself is legitimate; the defence is to narrow what a hijacked workload can reach, not to assume the model cannot be influenced. Model-artifact tampering (**T2**) covers a model that is swapped, backdoored, or pulled from an unverified source [14]; provenance verification proves *what* was pulled, not that the upstream training was clean, so we are explicit that weight-level backdoors remain out of scope. Stale evidence (**T9**) is the threat that a platform shows yesterday’s passing report as though it were today’s; it is mundane and, in our experience, the most common way that “we are compliant” becomes false without anyone noticing.

E. Scope

We treat three controls in depth: request lineage, access and model governance, and model provenance. We deliberately leave out multi-region operation, cost chargeback as a contribution, fine-tuning pipelines, retrieval quality, evaluation of model accuracy, and agent safety. Those are real concerns; they are simply not what this paper proves. We return to them in Section VIII.

TABLE I

THREAT MODEL. EACH THREAT MAPS TO A REQUIREMENT (TABLE II) AND, THROUGH IT, TO A CONTROL AND TO EVIDENCE.

ID	Threat	Req.
T1	Prompt or retrieved content leaks into logs or evidence	R3
T2	Unapproved or tampered model is served	R6, R9
T3	Unauthenticated or unauthorised invocation	R5
T4	Cross-tenant access to data or models	R7
T5	Unauthorised network egress / data exfiltration	R8
T6	Audit record is altered, deleted, or repudiated	R2
T7	Supply-chain compromise of image, chart, or pipeline	R11
T8	Indirect / RAG prompt injection drives a workload	R8, R3
T9	Stale or fabricated evidence shown as current	R12

III. REQUIREMENTS

We distilled the obligations of Section II into twelve requirements, each written so that a test can pass or fail on it. The discipline is deliberate: a requirement that cannot be checked is an aspiration, not a control. Table II states each requirement, the regulatory source it derives from, the control that enforces it, and the evidence it produces. We group them by the three controls plus a cross-cutting row.

The grouping mirrors the triangle from the introduction. Requirements **R1** through **R4** concern the *data* side: every request leaves an attributable, minimised, tamper-evident, queryable record. Requirements **R5** through **R8** concern *identity and model governance*: only approved identities reach only approved models, tenants are isolated, and egress is constrained. Requirements **R9** through **R11** concern *provenance*: every served model and every served image traces to a reproducible, approved origin. Requirement **R12** is the property that makes the rest credible over time: the evidence is regenerable and a release fails closed when it is missing or stale.

Two design choices in the table are worth defending. First, **R3** forbids storing raw prompts even though raw prompts would make debugging and lineage richer. We accept the loss because data minimisation is not negotiable under the GDPR and because a fingerprint (length plus SHA-256 over the canonical message list) is enough to prove that two requests carried the same content without retaining the content. Second, **R2** demands tamper-evidence rather than mere append-only storage. Append-only storage trusts the storage layer; a hash chain lets an auditor verify integrity without trusting it, which is the weaker assumption and therefore the better control.

The requirements also line up with the documentation and management-system view of the same obligations, not only the article-level view in the table. The provenance, supply-chain, and evidence-pack outputs populate the technical-documentation sections the EU AI Act enumerates in Annex IV [1], and the controls map onto the operational and lifecycle clauses of ISO/IEC 42001 [7]. Because each requirement is stated as a check that emits an artifact, that coverage is auditable rather than asserted.

Fig. 1. Request flow. (1) The caller authenticates. (2) The gateway applies access and model governance. (3) A redacted, hash-chained audit event is emitted. (4) The request is routed to an approved runtime. Tenants, RAG, and agent workspaces are isolated namespaces under default-deny networking.

IV. ARCHITECTURE AND DESIGN

The platform is organised so that the three controls are not bolted on but sit on the request path and in the delivery pipeline, where they can both enforce and observe. Figure 1 shows the request flow and where each control acts. We describe the design decision by decision, naming the requirement each serves and the alternative we rejected.

A. The gateway as the enforcement point

We place authentication, model allowlisting, admission, and budgeting in a single OpenAI-compatible gateway that every request must traverse (**R1**, **R5**, **R6**). The gateway is a small FastAPI service: a request-context middleware validates the request identifier, sandbox identifier, and W3C trace context [15], applies authentication, and then the handler resolves the model against a routing policy, validates admission, reserves budget, forwards to the runtime, and records a redacted audit event.

We rejected two alternatives. A *service-mesh sidecar* (for example, enforcing policy at the Envoy layer) would handle authentication and routing but has no model-level vocabulary; it cannot tell an approved model identifier from an unapproved one, nor compute a prompt fingerprint, without re-implementing the application semantics we already have. A *library embedded in each client* would push enforcement to the edge, where it is easy to bypass and impossible to attest centrally. A gateway concentrates the controls at one auditable choke point, which is exactly what makes the evidence complete: there is no second door.

Authentication accepts either an API-key digest or a bearer JWT validated against a JWKS endpoint (**R5**) [16]. The platform stores only SHA-256 digests of API keys and compares in constant time. The model allowlist (**R6**) is enforced twice, once as a static setting and once through a routing policy that maps approved model identifiers and aliases to backends; a request for any other identifier is rejected at admission with a machine-readable reason. Admission also bounds message count, prompt size, completion tokens, and temperature, and runs a set of secret-detection patterns over the prompt so that

TABLE II
 REQUIREMENTS DERIVED FROM REGULATION, THE CONTROL THAT ENFORCES EACH, AND THE EVIDENCE IT EMITS. SOURCES: AIA = EU AI ACT, DORA, GDPR, RMF = NIST AI RMF.

ID	Requirement (testable)	Source	Control	Evidence
R1	Every request records identity, model digest, data classification, timestamp, and policy decisions	AIA Art. 12; GDPR Art. 30	Lineage / audit trail	Audit event per request
R2	Audit records are tamper-evident; any modification or deletion is detectable	AIA traceability; DORA	Lineage / audit trail	Hash-chain verifier result
R3	Audit records contain no raw prompt or retrieved content	GDPR Art. 5(1)(c)	Lineage / audit trail	Redacted fields, SHA-256 fingerprints
R4	Lineage is queryable by request ID and time window in bounded effort	AIA Art. 12; RMF Measure	Lineage / audit trail	Auditor query output
R5	Only authenticated, authorised identities may invoke inference	DORA; GDPR Art. 32	Access governance	Auth config; blocked-attempt log
R6	Only catalog-approved models are servable; unapproved models are rejected	AIA risk mgmt.	Model governance	Allowlist; admission rejection
R7	Tenants are isolated; no cross-tenant data or model access	GDPR Art. 32	Access governance	Namespace, RBAC, NetworkPolicy set
R8	Egress is default-deny and governed by a reviewed allowlist	DORA; GDPR residency	Access governance	Egress catalog; CIDR policy result
R9	Every served model traces to a reproducible provenance record	AIA Art. 11; SLSA	Model provenance	Provenance record; digest match
R10	Promotion requires approval and separation of duties; provenance reproduces before serving	DORA change mgmt.	Model provenance	Promotion request; release gate
R11	Served images are signed, carry SBOM and build attestations, and pass vulnerability gates	DORA supply chain; SLSA	Supply chain	Cosign sig; SBOM; SARIF; attestation
R12	All evidence is regenerable on demand; a release fails closed on missing or stale evidence	continuous compliance	Cross-cutting	make evidence; strict release gate

obvious credential material is refused rather than forwarded. The pattern scan is a best-effort hygiene filter, not a guarantee: it catches common, unobfuscated credentials and is evadable by encoding or splitting, so we treat it as defence in depth rather than a control an attacker cannot pass.

B. Redacted lineage on the request path

For every request the gateway emits one structured audit event (**R1**). The event carries the request and trace identifiers, the sandbox, the backend and resolved model, the status, the latency, token usage, and a fingerprint of the payload: the message count, the roles, the prompt length, and a SHA-256 over the canonicalised message list. It never carries the prompt or the response text (**R3**). This is the data-minimisation decision from Section III made concrete: the fingerprint proves sameness and integrity of content without retaining content.

The gateway only emits the event. An append-only sink hash-chains the events into a tamper-evident log (**R2**), which we describe in Section V. We separate emission from chaining so that the chaining and verification can run out of band, on whatever durable store the customer already trusts, without adding latency to the request path.

C. Isolation and governed egress

Each tenant, RAG service, and coding-agent workspace runs in its own namespace with its own RBAC, quotas, and persistent volumes (**R7**). We chose namespace isolation within one cluster rather than a cluster per tenant because the latter multiplies operational and evidence surface without a matching security gain for the honest-but-curious model we target; where

a customer needs physical separation, the same charts deploy to separate clusters unchanged. Networking is default-deny: a workload reaches nothing until an explicit policy allows it. External egress is not expressed as raw CIDR rules but as references into a reviewed egress catalog, and a Kyverno policy rejects any NetworkPolicy that would allow a broad CIDR (**R8**). This matters most for the prompt-injection threat (**T8**): a hijacked agent cannot exfiltrate to an arbitrary host because the only destinations that exist are the ones a human approved.

D. GitOps delivery and policy-as-code

The platform is delivered by GitOps: Argo CD [10] syncs versioned Helm charts from a pinned revision, so the deployed state is always a named commit and never a manual change. Admission policy is enforced by Kyverno [11]: required labels, non-root and read-only-root containers, dropped capabilities, resource limits, a ban on floating image tags, the egress-CIDR restriction above, and keyless image-signature verification scoped to this project’s CI identity. We chose Kyverno over OPA/Gatekeeper [17] for no deep reason beyond fit: both express the same admission constraints, and the design does not depend on the choice. The decision that does matter is that policy lives in the repository as code, reviewed and versioned, so that “what is enforced” is itself an artifact with history rather than cluster state someone can quietly change.

E. Vendor neutrality

Every component above is either open source or first-party. The runtime is Ollama or vLLM; the policy engine, GitOps

controller, registry, and signing are CNCF or OpenSSF projects; nothing depends on a managed service from a specific cloud. This is a requirement of its own kind for the regulated buyer, who often must avoid a single-vendor dependency for resilience reasons that DORA makes explicit [2]. The local `kind` profile and the customer GPU profile share one repository, which is what lets the same evidence pipeline run in continuous integration and in production.

V. THE EVIDENCE MODEL

The architecture decides where controls act. The evidence model decides how a control becomes something a machine can check, and it is where most of the contribution lies. The guiding rule is simple to state and demanding to follow: for every requirement in Table II there must be a command that produces a machine-readable artifact whose pass or fail is unambiguous, and the whole set must regenerate from one entry point. Evidence that a human has to assemble by hand is evidence that rots between audits.

A. Evidence packs

The unit of evidence is the *evidence pack*. A single generator evaluates a fixed set of controls (30 in the version we evaluated) and writes both a JSON document and a human-readable Markdown summary. Each control is a record of the form (`area`, `status`, `summary`, `evidence`, `customer_action`): what was checked, whether it passed, a one-line summary, a pointer to the supporting artifact, and the action a customer must take to make the control real in their environment. Most controls are static checks, such as the presence and validity of a policy file or the success of a sub-check, and a subset can run live against a synced cluster (namespace existence, deployment readiness, persistent-volume binding). The pack is regenerated by `make evidence`, and `make evidence LIVE=1` adds the cluster checks. This is the concrete form of **R12**: one command, one current snapshot.

B. Hash-chained lineage and the auditor query

The gateway emits a redacted audit event per request (Section IV). To satisfy **R2** we layer a tamper-evident structure over the event stream. Writing H for SHA-256 and $\text{canon}(r_i)$ for the canonical serialisation of record r_i , each record carries the hash of its predecessor and its own hash chains over both:

$$h_i = H(h_{i-1} \parallel \text{canon}(r_i)), \quad h_0 = H(\text{genesis}).$$

This is the classic tamper-evident log construction [18], [19]; we use a linear chain rather than a Merkle tree because the auditor's queries are by request identifier and by time window, which a chain with an index serves directly, and because a chain is trivial to append on the request path's slow side. Altering, inserting, or deleting any record changes every subsequent hash, so a verifier that recomputes the chain detects the first divergence and names the record. The verifier reports the head hash, which a customer can anchor externally (for example, by periodically signing it) to extend tamper-evidence across backup and restore.

The *auditor query* answers **R4**: given a request identifier it returns the single record and its chain position; given a time window it returns the ordered slice and re-verifies that slice. Because the records are redacted by construction, the query can be handed to an auditor without exposing prompt content, which is precisely the combination that **R3** and **R4** ask for together.

```
{ "seq": 4213, "prev_hash": "9f1c...a0",
  "record": {
    "request_id": "req-7c2e...", "sandbox_id": "tenant-a",
    "backend": "vllm", "model": "Qwen/Qwen3-Coder-Next",
    "status_code": 200, "latency_ms": 412.7,
    "message_count": 2, "prompt_chars": 318,
    "prompt_sha256": "b35d...e1" },
  "record_hash": "44a8...c3" }
```

Listing 1. A redacted, chained audit record. No prompt text appears; the fingerprint proves content sameness and integrity.

C. Reproducible model provenance

A served model is governed only if one can say what it is and prove it. Each approved model carries a provenance record that must declare its source and source URI, an immutable reference, a digest, a license, a data classification, a risk tier, a promotion request, and the serving profiles it is allowed under (**R9**, **R10**). The digest is itself structured: an algorithm, a value, a *scope*, a verification mode, and a verification command. The scope distinguishes a *source-reference* digest (what a public registry advertises, pinned to an explicit upstream revision) from a *model-artifact* digest (the bytes in the customer's own model store). The verifier cross-checks every approved catalog model against its provenance record, confirms that the catalog and the record agree on status, license, classification, risk tier, promotion request, and source, and confirms that every referenced path exists. With verification enabled it re-fetches the digest from the source and asserts that it reproduces; source-reference digests that cannot be auto-fetched are reported as requiring manual confirmation rather than silently passing. The promotion gate additionally requires separation of duties and a pinned source revision, so a model cannot be promoted by the same hand that authored it or from a moving branch. Listing 2 shows a provenance record for one approved model.

```
modelId: qwen2.5:0.5b
status: approved
source: ollama-library
sourceUri: ollama://qwen2.5:0.5b
immutableRef: ollama-library/qwen2.5:0.5b@sha256:c5396e...0515
digest:
  algorithm: sha256
  value: c5396e06af294bd101...d3ab0515
  scope: model-artifact
  verificationMode: ollama-registry-model-layer
  verificationCommand: >
    curl -fsSL .../v2/library/qwen2.5/manifests/0.5b
    | jq -r '.layers[]|select(.mediaType=="...model").digest'
license: apache-2.0
dataClassification: internal
riskTier: low
```

```
promotionRequest: ../qwen2.5-local-lab-approved.
  yaml
catalogRef: platform/model-catalog/models.yaml
```

Listing 2. A model provenance record. The digest is reproducible through its verification command, and the catalog, promotion request, and serving profiles all resolve to files the verifier checks.

D. Policy-as-code and the release gate

Admission policy is itself evidence. The Kyverno policies (Section IV) are tested with positive and negative cases, so the artifact records both that a conforming workload is admitted and that a non-conforming one (a broad egress CIDR, an unsigned image, a privileged container) is rejected. The evidence pack captures the enforced policy set at a point in time.

The release gate ties everything together (**R12**). It evaluates eleven gates over the generated evidence: evaluation, load, restore drill, toolchain, egress, retention, SLO, quota, model provenance, supply chain, and the evidence pack itself. Each gate has explicit thresholds; the load gate, for instance, requires the error rate below 5%, p95 below 10 s, and p99 below 15 s. These latency bounds are deliberately loose because they are sized for real GPU inference under load at a customer’s chosen concurrency, not for the gateway overhead measured in Section VI-B; a customer tightens them to their own service-level objective, and the gate is designed to fail closed when a regressed run breaches them. The gate has two modes. In its normal mode it accepts the checked-in sample artifacts, which exist to prove report shape and gate behaviour. In strict mode (`make release-gate-strict`) it rejects any evidence whose filename marks it a sample and any evidence older than a configurable age, and fails closed if a required input is missing. Strict mode is the answer to **T9**: a release cannot be cut against yesterday’s, or fabricated, evidence.

E. Supply-chain attestations

For **R11**, the continuous-integration pipeline signs each image and Helm chart with keyless Cosign [20], [21], generates an SBOM in SPDX form [22], [23], scans for vulnerabilities and fails on HIGH or CRITICAL findings, and publishes SLSA build-provenance and SBOM attestations [24], [25] together with an OpenSSF Scorecard result [26]. Admission then verifies, through the Kyverno signature policy, that the running image was signed by this project’s CI identity and no other. The supply-chain evidence summary records, per image, the SBOM, the scan result, and the checksum manifest, and the release gate refuses to pass if any HIGH or CRITICAL finding remains.

F. One command

The properties above are individually unremarkable; tamper-evident logs, SBOMs, and admission policies are all established practice. What the evidence model contributes is their composition behind a single regeneration path and a single fail-closed gate, mapped one-to-one onto requirements that came from regulation. The reviewer, or the auditor, runs one command, watches the pack regenerate, and reads a result that is either current and passing or explicitly not. That property, more than any individual control, is what turns “private” into “provable”.

VI. EVALUATION

We evaluate the claim from three directions. First, does the design actually defend the threat model, and is the defence machine-verifiable rather than asserted (Section VI-A)? Second, what does the governance layer cost at runtime (Section VI-B)? Third, does the design hold up in the realistic settings it was built for (Section VI-C)? All measurements were taken on an AMD Ryzen 7 5800X3D (8 cores, 16 threads) running the gateway under Python 3.12; the functional and security checks need no GPU.

A. Security and machine-verifiability

Table III is the central artifact of this prong: for each threat it names the control that mitigates it and the evidence that proves the mitigation. The table is not aspirational. Every row in the “evidence” column corresponds to a file an evaluator can regenerate, and the two rows that are most often merely claimed in practice, tamper-evidence and access enforcement, we verified directly.

Tamper-evidence. We exercised the hash-chained log (Section V-B) on both synthetic records and the real audit stream emitted by the governed gateway during the cost experiment. The verifier confirms a clean chain of 112,127 real records and recomputes its head. We then performed two tampering attacks. A naive edit, changing one stored record’s status code without recomputing hashes, is caught at exactly that record by the internal consistency check (it reports `record_hash_mismatch` at the edited sequence). A sophisticated attack that re-chains every record from the edit forward produces an internally consistent log, but its head no longer matches the externally anchored head, so the anchor check reports `anchor_mismatch`. The auditor query returns the single record for a given request identifier and a verified contiguous slice for a time window. This is the demonstration the design is built around: one altered record out of more than a hundred thousand is detected, automatically, and named. The guarantee holds under the honest-but-curious model of Section II and assumes the chain head is anchored outside the store the operator controls, which we treat as a deployment requirement and revisit in Section VIII.

Access enforcement. The conformance suite attempts a fixed set of forbidden actions against the fully governed gateway and asserts both the status code and the machine-readable rejection reason. An unauthenticated request is rejected at the boundary with 401. A request for a model outside the allowlist is rejected with `model_not_allowed`. An oversized prompt, a prompt carrying credential material, a streaming request when streaming is disabled, an over-long message list, and an over-large completion-token request are each rejected at admission with their specific reason. A second request in a sandbox whose budget is exhausted is throttled with 429 and `sandbox_request_budget_exceeded`. A positive control, a well-formed authorised request, succeeds with 200, which confirms the gateway is enforcing policy rather than simply refusing traffic. All checks pass. Each blocked attempt is itself an evidence item.

TABLE III

THREAT TO CONTROL TO EVIDENCE. THE FINAL COLUMN NAMES THE ARTIFACT THAT AN EVALUATOR REGENERATES TO CHECK THE MITIGATION.

Threat	Control	Mechanism	Evidence (regenerable)
T1 content leak	Redacted lineage	Length + SHA-256 fingerprint, never raw text	Audit record schema; conformance secret-block
T2 bad model	Provenance + allowlist	Reproducible digest; gateway allowlist	model-provenance report; admission rejection
T3 unauth access	Authentication	API-key digest or JWT/JWKS	conformance 401 on missing credential
T4 cross-tenant	Namespace isolation	RBAC, per-namespace PVC, default-deny	Policy tests; evidence-pack isolation control
T5 egress / exfil	Governed egress	Catalog references; Kyverno CIDR deny	egress-governance report; policy test
T6 audit tamper	Hash-chained log	Linear SHA-256 chain + anchor	audit-chain verifier flags mutated record
T7 supply chain	Signed artifacts	Cosign, SBOM, SLSA attestation, scan	supply-chain summary; admission verify
T8 prompt injection	Egress narrowing + budgets	Default-deny, sandbox budget cap	conformance budget 429; egress report
T9 stale evidence	Strict release gate	Reject sample and stale artifacts	release-gate-strict failure on old input

B. Cost of compliance

The natural objection to any governance layer is that it slows the system down. We measured the cost two ways: a microbenchmark that isolates the governance logic, and an end-to-end measurement of the governed gateway under load.

Governance logic in isolation. We timed the real governance functions directly, with no network in the path, over hundreds of thousands of iterations each (Figure 2). The full governance path, authentication, model routing, admission including the prompt secret scan, budget reservation, and the audit fingerprint and serialisation, costs about 28 microseconds of CPU per request. The cost is not evenly spread. The prompt secret scan dominates admission at roughly 14.7 μ s, audit fingerprinting and serialisation accounts for about 9.3 μ s, and budget reservation for about 3.8 μ s. Authentication (0.5 μ s), the model allowlist (0.13 μ s), and model routing (0.13 μ s) are effectively free. The two controls that an auditor cares about most, who-called and which-model, are the cheapest; the cost is in scanning and recording, both of which scale with prompt length rather than with the number of policies.

End-to-end under load. We then ran the real gateway against a constant-latency mock backend, which holds model inference fixed so that any latency difference is attributable to the gateway. The load is closed-loop: a fixed number of virtual users each issue a request and wait for its response before issuing the next, so there is no coordinated-omission artifact from a fixed arrival schedule. We compared three configurations: the baseline (the client calling the backend directly), the ungoverned gateway (proxying only), and the fully governed gateway (all controls on), sweeping concurrency from one to thirty-two and, separately, the backend think-time

Fig. 2. Per-control CPU cost of the governance path, measured in isolation. The full path is about 28 μ s per request; secret scanning and audit recording dominate, while authentication and the model allowlist are sub-microsecond. Error bars are 95% confidence intervals over seven trials of 200,000 iterations each and are smaller than the labels.

from zero to half a second. Each cell is five repeats of a two-second warmup, discarded, followed by eight measured seconds; we report the median across repeats with a Student's t 95% confidence interval, using t rather than a bootstrap because five samples is too few for a percentile bootstrap. Figure 3 plots the median latency against concurrency.

Two findings stand out. First, the governance controls add little latency. At a single in-flight request the ungoverned gateway answers in 3.97 ms at the median (95% CI 3.93 to 4.00) and the fully governed gateway in 4.27 ms (95% CI 4.22 to 4.33), a difference of 0.31 ms whose confidence intervals do not overlap; the governance cost is therefore resolvable rather

Fig. 3. Median latency against concurrency. The governed and ungoverned gateway curves nearly coincide, so governance adds little; the gap to the direct baseline is the cost of the proxy hop itself, not of the controls. Error bars are 95% t confidence intervals over five repeats and are typically within the marker.

than lost in run-to-run noise. The tail does not blow up: at this operating point the governed gateway’s p95 and p99 are 4.82 and 5.28 ms against the ungoverned 4.54 and 5.12 ms, so the added tail latency is no larger than the added median. The governed and ungoverned curves in Figure 3 track each other across the whole concurrency range; the wider gap, 1.8 to 2.1 ms, is between either gateway and the direct baseline at 2.17 ms, and that is the cost of inserting a proxy hop, not the cost of governing it. Second, governance has a modest throughput cost, and Figure 4 shows it across the whole load regime. Both gateway configurations saturate a single worker at concurrency four, where the ungoverned worker peaks at about 510 requests per second and the governed worker at about 448, a 12% reduction whose confidence intervals do not overlap (510 ± 34 against 448 ± 5); past that knee both fold back as queuing latency climbs, an effect the rising latency curves cannot show. The governed curve tracks the ungoverned one throughout: the inset zooms the gateway region so the two bands and their intervals are legible, and governed throughput stays between 87.8% and 93.1% of ungoverned across the sweep, worst at the concurrency-four peak, so the cost is bounded rather than growing with load. Most of that gap is the synchronous audit-log write, which a production deployment moves to an off-path sink; the remaining controls are sub-millisecond per request, as the microbenchmark shows. The direct baseline, talking to the backend without a gateway, sustains about 2,290 requests per second on the same hardware, again the proxy hop rather than the controls. The honest way to read a cost-of-compliance result is the governed-minus-ungoverned gap, and that gap is 0.31 ms of latency and about 12% of peak per-worker throughput, the latter dominated by audit I/O that need not be synchronous.

Sweeping the backend think-time tells the same story from the other direction. The governance layer adds a fixed cost of about 0.31 ms per request, independent of how long inference takes. With the backend delayed by 50, 200, and

Fig. 4. Throughput against concurrency for the same sweep as Figure 3. Both gateway configurations saturate a single worker at concurrency four, where the ungoverned gateway peaks at 510 requests per second and the governed gateway at 448, a 12% reduction; past that knee both fold back as latency climbs. The inset zooms the gateway region: the governed curve holds 87.8% to 93.1% of the ungoverned throughput across the sweep, so the governance cost is small and bounded rather than growing with load. The direct baseline sustains about 2,290 requests per second; the wide gap to either gateway is the cost of the proxy hop, not of the controls. Error bars are 95% t confidence intervals over five repeats.

500 milliseconds to emulate real inference, that fixed cost is no longer separately resolvable: the governed-minus-ungoverned difference falls within the run-to-run variance of a backend that itself varies by several milliseconds. The measured difference is 0.19 ms at a 50 ms think-time and then changes sign, reaching -1.9 ms at 200 ms and $+6.8$ ms at 500 ms. A cost that is sometimes negative is the signature of noise, not of a fixed overhead: a real 0.31 ms governance cost cannot make the governed path faster than the ungoverned one, so once inference dominates, the governance term is below the noise floor of the measurement. Set against the microbenchmark’s 28 μ s of governance computation and inference latencies measured in hundreds of milliseconds, the governance layer is well under one percent of end-to-end latency. Once real inference time is present, which is the deployment case rather than the exception, the cost of governance disappears into the model’s own variance.

Against an existing gateway. To place these figures in context we ran the same harness against LiteLLM [27], a widely used open-source OpenAI-compatible proxy, in front of the same mock backend. Measured the same way, as added latency over the direct path at a single in-flight request and each against its own concurrent direct baseline in the same run, LiteLLM adds about 5.9 ms, against 2.1 ms for our fully governed gateway. A feature-rich proxy that performs no compliance work is therefore heavier than our gateway with every control enabled. This is the clearest statement of the paper’s cost claim: the governance layer is not what makes an LLM gateway expensive.

C. Case-study validation

Two scenarios the platform was built for show that the design holds beyond a microbenchmark.

Regulated offline tenant. A tenant that must run fully air-gapped receives a namespace with default-deny networking, a model whose provenance record pins a customer-model-store digest rather than a public registry reference, a per-sandbox budget, and an audit chain anchored to the customer’s own store. The evidence an auditor receives is the evidence pack plus the chain head: which models were approved (catalog and provenance report), that no unapproved model could be served (allowlist plus admission rejection log), that no egress was possible beyond the empty catalog (egress report), and a tamper-evident record of every request. None of this requires the auditor to trust the operator’s word.

Customer handoff. When the platform is handed to a customer to operate, the handoff is gated on strict evidence: the release gate is run with current, non-sample artifacts, the model digests are replaced with the customer’s own, and authentication is wired to the customer identity provider. The handoff artifact is the strict release-gate result, which fails closed if any of the eleven gates lacks current evidence. The case study makes the continuous-compliance property concrete: the same command that a developer runs in continuous integration is the command that produces the audit-ready evidence at handoff.

VII. RELATED WORK

LLM serving systems. A line of work has made model serving fast and memory-efficient. vLLM [4] introduced PagedAttention; Orca [28] introduced iteration-level scheduling; KServe [29] standardises model serving on Kubernetes; gateways such as LiteLLM [27] unify many model APIs behind one interface; and the Kubernetes Gateway API Inference Extension [30] is standardising model-aware routing as a vendor-neutral substrate. These systems are complementary to ours and in fact one of them (vLLM) is the runtime we target. The inference extension in particular defines where inference traffic flows, not the evidence that flow must produce, which is the layer we add. None of them is concerned with producing the evidence an auditor needs. They optimise the throughput and ergonomics of serving; we take serving as given and ask what record it leaves behind. Our gateway deliberately does not compete on serving performance, which is why we route to vLLM rather than re-implement it.

Policy-as-code and Kubernetes security. OPA/Gatekeeper [17] and Kyverno [11] bring admission control and policy enforcement to Kubernetes, and we use Kyverno directly. These engines are general: they constrain pods, images, and network policy. What they do not provide on their own is the application-level vocabulary of a model catalog, a prompt fingerprint, or a per-request lineage record, nor the mapping from a regulatory clause to a passing or failing check. We sit above the policy engine and use it as one mechanism among several.

Software supply-chain provenance. SLSA [24], in-toto [25], and Sigstore [20], [21] define how to attest the provenance of build artifacts, and our supply-chain control is built on them. The OpenSSF Model Signing effort [31] extends the same signing machinery to model artifacts of any format. Our contribution here is not a new provenance scheme but the

wiring of model provenance into serving: a reproducible digest that distinguishes what a registry advertises (a source-reference digest) from what a customer actually stores (a model-artifact digest), verified at admission so that an unattested model is not servable. A signature proves who produced a set of bytes; our record additionally re-derives the digest from a pinned upstream reference, and a served model whose bytes do not reproduce is rejected. A machine-readable AI bill of materials [32] for each approved model is a natural evidence artifact on top of this, and one the evidence pack can carry.

Tamper-evident logging. The hash-chained audit log is a direct application of established techniques: Merkle’s hash construction [19], Crosby and Wallach’s tamper-evident logs [18], and Certificate Transparency [33]. We claim no novelty in the data structure. The contribution is its use as the lineage substrate for inference requests under a data-minimisation constraint, so that the record is both tamper-evident and free of prompt content. Recent work applies the same construction to LLMs directly: AuditableLLM [34] records model-update events, such as fine-tuning and unlearning, as a tamper-evident, third-party-verifiable trail. That work audits how a model changes over time; we audit how a served request is handled, at request granularity on the serving path and under a redaction constraint that keeps prompt content out of the record. They are complementary lineage layers for the same system.

Compliance automation. NIST’s OSCAL [35] expresses control catalogs and assessment results in machine-readable form, and AI Cards [36] propose a machine-readable format for the technical documentation the EU AI Act expects; the broader “compliance as code” practice automates control checks. These efforts give a language for controls, assessments, and documentation; they do not, by themselves, bind those controls to a live AI serving path or measure what enforcing them costs. AI Cards describe what a system should document; our evidence model regenerates that record from the running system and fails closed when it is missing. It is a concrete, AI-serving-specific instantiation of the compliance-as-code idea, with the binding made explicit through the requirements table and the costs measured.

Governance platforms for AI. The closest system to ours is AAGATE [37], a Kubernetes-native governance platform aligned to the NIST AI RMF that combines a service mesh, policy-as-code, immutable audit logging, and signed supply-chain artifacts. We differ on scope and on evidence. AAGATE governs autonomous *agents*, with agent identity, tool gateways, and multi-agent interaction, whereas we govern general LLM serving; its regulatory framing is the NIST RMF and the EU AI Act, whereas we add the GDPR data-minimisation and DORA supply-chain obligations a regulated European buyer is held to; its provenance is at the container and image layer, whereas ours reaches the model artifact with a reproducible digest; and, most concretely, AAGATE reports no measurement of what its governance costs at runtime, which is the question our evaluation answers. The two designs share a substrate and the conviction that governance belongs in the platform, and they reach different halves of the problem.

AI-specific security. Work on indirect prompt injection [12], [13] and training-data poisoning [14] characterises threats that are specific to LLM-integrated systems. We do not solve these problems. We design the perimeter so that their blast radius is bounded: default-deny egress limits what an injected instruction can reach, and provenance verification narrows what an attacker can substitute. We are explicit throughout that these are defence-in-depth measures, not guarantees.

Confidential computing. Trusted execution environments and confidential VMs protect data and models while in use, including for inference, and are an active direction for private AI; recent measurements put the cost of confidential inference at under ten percent of throughput on CPU trusted execution environments and single-digit percentages on current GPU ones [38]. They are complementary to our work rather than competing with it: a TEE strengthens the confidentiality of the runtime, while our concern is the evidence that a request was governed and recorded, at a cost an order of magnitude smaller. A deployment could combine the two, running the governed gateway and runtime inside confidential hardware and anchoring the audit chain to a hardware-rooted measurement; we treat that composition as future work.

In short, the pieces we compose are individually well understood, and one recent platform assembles a strikingly similar stack for agents. The gap we fill is a specific one: a vendor-neutral private-LLM serving platform whose three core controls emit machine-checkable evidence mapped to specific regulatory obligations, the GDPR’s data minimisation and DORA’s supply-chain duties among them, whose provenance reaches the model artifact, and whose runtime governance cost is measured rather than assumed.

VIII. DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

What the measurement does and does not show. Our cost result isolates the governance layer. The microbenchmark (Section VI-B) times the real governance functions with no network in the path, so it is a clean per-request CPU figure. The end-to-end measurement runs the real gateway against a mock backend, which lets us attribute the latency delta to the gateway rather than to model inference, but it does not measure GPU serving throughput. We are comfortable with this division because the paper’s claim is about the cost of *governance*, not about the throughput of any particular model. A study of governed serving on production GPUs, sweeping model sizes and real workloads, is worthwhile and is future work. We expect the relative overhead there to be smaller, not larger, because inference latency grows while the governance cost stays fixed.

Threats to validity. The cost numbers come from one CPU (an eight-core Ryzen), one node, and a loopback network, so the absolute microseconds are specific to that microarchitecture and will differ elsewhere; we make no cross-hardware claim about the absolute figures. The claim we do defend is relative and more robust. Because the governance work is a fixed per-request cost while inference latency dominates end-to-end time, the sub-percent share holds across hardware, and the

microbenchmark and the end-to-end delta agree on the size of that fixed cost. The mock backend is a deliberate instrument rather than a shortcut, because holding inference time constant is what isolates the governance term, and a single controlled node is the right place to measure a per-request CPU cost. What a single node does not exercise, namely GPU contention, real network variance, and multi-tenant interference, is exactly the production-GPU study named above.

Limited external comparison. We compare against one external gateway, the LiteLLM proxy (Section VI-B), which places our overhead in context: a feature-rich open-source proxy in front of the same backend is itself slower than our governed gateway, so the governance controls are not what makes a gateway expensive. We did not compare against a service-mesh policy hop or a managed gateway, and a broader cross-system study remains future work.

Threat-model boundaries. We target an honest-but-curious insider for the tamper-evidence claim. An attacker who fully controls the storage layer and the chain head can still rewrite history; anchoring the head externally (signing it periodically) raises the bar but does not eliminate the assumption. Provenance verification proves which bytes were served, not that the upstream training was clean, so model-weight backdoors are out of scope. Network isolation and cross-tenant separation are enforced by Kubernetes NetworkPolicy and RBAC and validated by policy tests and on a `kind` cluster; we did not attempt a red-team of the isolation, and a determined evaluation of namespace escape is beyond this paper.

Authentication scope. The cost measurement uses API-key authentication, the platform’s default for business endpoints. JWT validation against a JWKS endpoint adds asymmetric signature verification, which is more expensive per request, although the cost is amortised by JWKS caching. We did not benchmark the JWT path under load and note it as a gap.

Generality. The design assumes a Kubernetes substrate and an OpenAI-compatible request shape. Organisations that cannot run Kubernetes, or that need a fundamentally different request contract, would have to adapt the gateway. The evidence model itself is more portable: the idea of mapping requirements to a one-command, fail-closed evidence pack does not depend on Kubernetes and could be applied to other serving substrates.

Future work. We park the items we deliberately left out of scope. Multi-region operation and data residency across regions, cost chargeback as a first-class control, fine-tuning and its provenance, retrieval quality, evaluation of model accuracy and bias, and agent safety are all real and all absent here by design. Each could become a fourth, fifth, or sixth control with its own requirement and evidence; the discipline that kept this paper focused was to prove three controls fully rather than gesture at many.

IX. CONCLUSION

Running a language model on your own cluster keeps the data at home. It does not, on its own, answer the questions a regulator or an auditor will ask. We set out to close the distance between a private model and a provable one, and we did it by

treating the auditor’s questions as engineering requirements: which identity called which model over which data, and where is the tamper-evident record.

The result is a vendor-neutral Kubernetes architecture whose three controls, request lineage, access and model governance, and model provenance, each emit evidence a machine can check, and an evidence model that regenerates that evidence with one command and refuses to pass when the proof is missing or stale. We evaluated the design against its threat model, showed that forbidden actions are blocked and that a single altered audit record is caught, and measured what the governance layer costs. On commodity hardware the full governed path adds about 28 microseconds of processing per request, a sub-percent fraction of end-to-end latency once inference is present.

The broader claim is modest and, we think, useful: provable compliance for private LLM serving is not a tax that has to be weighed against performance. Built into the request path and the delivery pipeline rather than bolted on before an audit, its cost is small and bounded. The platform, the benchmark harness, and the scripts that produced every number here are released so that the claim can be checked rather than taken on faith.

ETHICS AND RESPONSIBLE USE

This work strengthens the governance and auditability of systems that organisations already operate, so its primary effect is defensive. Two boundaries deserve explicit statement. First, several controls are best-effort rather than guarantees: the prompt secret scan is evadable by obfuscation, and the tamper-evident log assumes an externally anchored chain head and the honest-but-curious operator of Section II. We present them as defence in depth, not as proofs, because presenting them otherwise would mislead an adopter about the protection they provide. Second, the platform processes prompts and retrieved content that may contain personal or regulated data; the design minimises what is retained, keeping redacted and fingerprinted records rather than raw text, but operators remain responsible for lawful processing, retention, and residency. The artifact contains no personal data: every measurement used synthetic prompts against a mock backend. The controls described here reduce, rather than expand, the blast radius of misuse, and we see no dual-use risk beyond that inherent in any model-serving platform.

ARTIFACT AVAILABILITY

The platform described here is released as the PRIVATE-AI-PLATFORM-KIT project under the Apache 2.0 license at <https://github.com/RamazanKara/private-ai-platform-kit>; the revision evaluated in this paper is tagged `v1.1.0-paper` (commit `abaa4cf`) and archived at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21047804>. The benchmark harness, the external-baseline runner, the configurations, and the analysis scripts that produced every figure and table are included with the artifact, and a companion `PAPER.md` maps each numbered claim and figure to the command that regenerates it against that pinned revision. Because the absolute latencies depend on the host, a reviewer

reproducing on different hardware should expect the same governed-minus-ungoverned delta and the same sub-percent share rather than identical microsecond figures; the harness reports both.

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